

Monograph

Silage: Potential use as livestock green fodder

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Introduction

When each household only has one dairy cow, how can the nutrition of farmers' milking animals be improved? Wheat or maize straw, along with hay and concentrated diets, are the main fodders available throughout the harsh continental winter. To improve rumen function in cattle, it is absolutely necessary to supplement the diet with green fodder. As a result, winter feed crops should be developed, finding enough feed to maintain good milk production throughout the cold months is a constant challenge for smallholder farmers with constrained production capacity. Due to the increased prices paid for animal feed in the winter, many are obliged to buy hay, concentrates, or silage only to keep their animals alive and are unable to profit. The product created when any green plant material is placed in an area where it can ferment without the presence of air is known as silage. Green feeds are preserved as silage when they are in abundance to meet the demand for high-quality feed during the lean season Lamidi and Ologbose, (2014). Silage is the green, succulent roughage that has been mostly retained in its original state, with little to no loss of the nutritional components of the feed. Ensilage refers to the method of preserving green fodder. The container in which silage is produced is a silo. The most appetising and nutrient-dense silage has a DM (dry matter) of 25–35% and is green and fruity (Sikora et al., 2019).

What is silage?

Through a natural "pickling" process, forage that has been cultivated while still green and nutritious can be preserved Shishi and agbo, (2018). When bacteria ferment the sugars in the forage plants in an enclosed space (a "silo") without air, lactic acid is created. This type of fodder preservation is referred to as "ensiled forage" or "silage," and it can remain intact for up to three years. Silage is delicious to livestock.

What do you need for silage making?

- In order to produce silage in large quantities, you would need the right agricultural equipment, such as tractors, silage baling machines, etc.
- To store the prepared silage, you would want a silo or a trench.
- It's crucial to realise that additions like molasses, urea, salt, and formic acid can considerably improve the quality of silage preparation.

Different types of silages

In general, the common classification under which the silages are separated are:

- High-moisture silage (less than 30% dry matter)
- Medium-moisture silage (30 – 40% dry matter)
- Low-moisture silage (< 30% dry matter) (Paul et al. (2018).

Silage preparation

1. Ensile crops with a high moisture content while adding preservatives and chemicals.
2. The ideal crop to use for making silage is one that has just begun to blossom.
3. Molasses can be used as a source of carbohydrates if a crop (such as legumes) lacks soluble carbohydrates.
4. To get the air out of the silo, the crop needs to be firmly trodden or pounded.
5. Before ensiling, the crop should be chopped.
6. The lower the cut length, the higher the quality of the silage.

Silo

1. For the storage and preservation of high moisture feed as silage, it is an airtight construction.
2. A tower, trench, or hole in the ground where green feed is kept while being processed into silage.
3. Precautions should be taken when building a silo.
4. The height and depth of the silo depend on the demand for silage, the area's water level, the cost of construction and the equipment available for filling the silo. The top of the silo should be completely covered with a water-proof material, such as plastic sheet, concrete slabs, etc., to prevent the growth of mould.
5. Normally the height of a cylindrical silo is taken double of its diameter

Crops suitable for silage making

Crops having thick, solid stems and rich in soluble carbohydrate are best for silage preparation e.g. Maize sorghum, bajra and Silage can also be prepared from oat, berseem after wilting to 35-40% DM

Stage of crops suitable for ensiling

Maize-dent stage; Oat, sorghum, Bajra-milk or dough stage, Berseem, Lucerne-20-25% bloom stage, natural grasses-early flowering stage.

Method of Silage Preparation

1. Levelling the pit and preparing the silo at the intended position are the first steps in the silage-making process.
2. The crop that is suitable for creating silage is first cut into little pieces that are between 2 and 4 cm long and wilted until it reaches 35% DM.
3. Molasses (@ 3 to 5%) can be applied as a silage addition to supply soluble carbohydrates for effective bacterial fermentation.
4. Salt (0.5 g) and urea (1 g) can be added to increase the palatability and nitrogen content, respectively. The whole material is thoroughly mixed and then filled tightly in the silo. Silo should be filled rapidly and should not be left open. It should be sealed as soon as possible and pressed so that no air pocket is left in the silo otherwise chances of mould formation led to spoilage.
5. To seal the silo after filling it, cover it with a layer of earth or mud and then a polythene sheet.

6. After 45 days of ensiling, silage can be removed and utilised to feed animals. When taking the silage out of the silo, caution should be used. After the silo has been opened for feeding, it shouldn't be allowed to decay. The least amount of face should ever be revealed at once, and covers should be kept firmly in place for as long as feasible.

Characteristics of good quality silage

1. The aroma, physical state, PH, ammonium nitrogen, volatile acids, and lactic acid are the primary factors that affect the quality of silage.
2. The forage needs to have a high-water soluble sugar content (more than 5% on a dry-matter basis) in order to ferment well.
3. It should be green, yellow, or golden brown in colour. Pleasant or vinegar-like aroma, Texture: firm, pH: 3.5–4.2, lactic acid content: 5–15%, butyric acid: none or very little (less than 0.2), and ammonia nitrogen: less than 10% of total nitrogen.

Advantages of Silage Making

1. It tastes good, has a mild laxative effect, and provides succulent nutrition in times of scarcity.
2. Nutrient loss is less compared to other preservation techniques.
3. Less space is needed for storage compared to hay.
4. By preventing pests and insects from finishing their life cycles as a result of early crop harvest, it aids in biological management of pests and insects.
6. Silage can be made from plants that have thick stems and are therefore unsuitable for hay production, as well as when the weather does not allow for the production of hay.

Disadvantages of Silage Making

1. Building a silo is expensive.
2. If silos are not properly prepared, there could be a significant loss of nutrients.
3. There is a 5-20% loss of dry matter as a result of fermentation.
4. If air enters the silo, considerable carotene is lost.

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